

Title:

Security Analysis of Virtual Machine Monitoring in Cloud Computing
Environments

Abstract

Cloud computing adoption in corporate infrastructure has highlighted significant security concerns, especially in monitoring virtual machines (VMs) across numerous physical servers with minimal overhead. This report explores potential attacks on Virtualized Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI) and vulnerabilities of Virtual Machine Monitors (VMMs), offering insights into securing them effectively.

To gather comprehensive resource usage data, either hypervisor monitoring or VMMs are necessary. For safeguarding VCCI and VMMs, techniques like Encryption and Key Management (EKM), Access Control Mechanisms (ACM), Virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPM), Virtual Firewalls (VF), and Trusted Virtual Domains (TVDs) are vital.

Security issues in Software as a Service (SaaS) include insecure APIs, data protection, insecure access management, and shared technology concerns, highlighting the need for robust security measures. Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) security challenges encompass administrative commands to cloud providers, virtual machines, and user interaction with virtual machines via network services.

The Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM) manages VMs in the VCCI, crucial for client operations. However, VMMs and VCCI are susceptible to various attacks, including VM-to-VM cross-side channel attacks. Security solutions that segregate VMMs, guest/host OS, and physical hardware are essential for protecting against such attacks.

Key security techniques such as Encryption and Key Management (EKM), Access Control Mechanisms (ACMs), Intrusion Detection Tools (IDTs), Virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPM), Virtual Firewalls (VFs), and Trusted Virtual Domains (TVDs) are crucial for securing a VCCI.

In conclusion, securing cloud computing environments poses significant challenges, particularly in protecting VMMs from attacks. Future research should focus on developing and implementing robust security strategies across various layers of cloud resources.

Key words: Cloud Computing, Virtualized Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI), Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM), Security Threats, Virtual Machines (VMs), Encryption and Key Management (EKM), Access Control Mechanisms (ACMs), Virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPM), Virtual Firewalls (VFs), Trusted Virtual Domains (TVDs), Hypervisors, Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Software as a Service (SaaS), Security Challenges, Cross-VM Attacks, Resource Monitoring

1. Introduction

The implementation of cloud computing in a corporate infrastructure raises security concerns. Monitoring hundreds of virtual machines running on several physical servers requires a high level of security and little overhead. The purpose of this report is to explain the numerous attacks that may be made against the Virtualized Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI), and to explain the vulnerabilities of VMMs and how to secure them.

To get comprehensive resource usage data, either hypervisor monitoring or VMMs will be required. For the resource monitoring experiment (TVDs), techniques for safeguarding a VCCI, VMMs, such as Encryption and Key Management (EKM), Access Control Mechanisms (ACM), Virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPM), Virtual Firewalls (VF), and Trusted Virtual Domains, are necessary [1] [2] [3].

2.0. FIVE Security Issues with SaaS

Cloud computing security concerns include Insecure APIs (application program interfaces), Data protection, Insecure access management, and Shared technology issues:

- I. Security of hypervisors.
- II. VM-to-VM cross-side channel attacks.

A report of attacks between virtual machines is presented, as well as how we protected ourselves against attacks. As a result, Virtual Machines can share physical memory, Central Processing Units (CPUs), network buffers, and DRAM of physical machines. The attack process consists of two steps:

- a) Physical and virtual machines are placed on the same physical machine.
- b) Taking advantage of shared resources.

A CPU cache leak attack is described as follows:

Check the load on the other virtual web server.

Keys for AES and RSA can be extracted.

Analyzing the timing of keystrokes.

From the SSH terminal, extract user passwords.

3.0 Security Issues In The Cloud Environment

Issues related to the security of infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS)

IaaS offers resources including servers, storage, networks, and other computing resources as virtualized systems that can be accessed via the Internet. There are essentially three different ways to access cloud resources across a network: administrative commands to the cloud provider, administrative commands to virtual machines, and user interaction with virtual machines via network services [4].

4.0. Infrastructures for cloud computing under threat from security

Virtual Machine Monitor, which is running in physical infrastructure, manages VMs, which are used by clients running on virtual machines housed in the Virtual Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI). A software layer called the VMM, or hypervisor enables many Virtual Machines to run on a physical computer. The two sorts of hypervisors we have are type 1 and type 2. Type 2 functions alongside the host OS. Figure 1 depicts Type 2 as consisting of Xen and Kernel Virtual Machine (KVM).

VMware ESX, Microsoft Hyper-V, XenVMware workstation, Microsoft Virtual PC, KVM

Figure 1. Types of hypervisors [5]

Side Channel Cross-VM Attacks

Any part of VCCI that can have an impact on others is vulnerable to attack due to security flaws. The infrastructure must be safeguarded by adopting security solutions that segregate the VMM, guest/host OS, and physical hardware from one another's side effects [2]. In this paper, we discuss techniques to defeat attackers on VCCI and vulnerabilities of VMMs. discovered two significant VCCI attacks (VM to VM and VM to Hypervisor), as depicted in Figure 2.

Attacks can occur through the three main hypervisor vulnerabilities (VM hopping, VM escape, and VM mobility) as shown in the above graphic. VM hopping: This attack may result in a denial of service, rendering user-accessible resources inaccessible. VM Escape: This flaw enables a VM running at the guest level to attack its host. VM Mobility: In a VCCI, the ability of VMs to switch between different physical hosts is referred to as VM mobility [5] [6].

5.0. Describe Security Threats to Virtualized Cloud Computing Infrastructures A multi-tenant Cloud

Computing Infrastructure(CCI) consists of several Virtual Machines (VMs) running on the same physical platform by using virtualization techniques. The VMs are monitored and managed by kernel-based software i.e., Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM) or hypervisor which is the main component of Virtualized Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI). Due to software-based vulnerabilities, VMMs are compromised by security attacks that may take place from inside or outside attackers. To formulate a secure VCCI, VMM must be protected by implementing strong security techniques such as Encryption and Key Management (EKM), Access Control Mechanisms (ACMs), Intrusion Detection Tools (IDTs), Virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPM), Virtual Firewalls (VFs) and Trusted Virtual Domains (TVDs). In this work, we describe the techniques of virtualizing a CCI, types of attacks on VCCI, vulnerabilities of VMMs, and we describe the significance of security techniques for securing a VCCI.

Figure 2. Attack on Virtual Cloud Computing Infrastructure (VCCI).

5.1. Key Management and Encryption (EKM)

The popular encryption technique that can be applied to VCCI, including symmetric and asymmetric algorithms, is encryption and key management (EKM). With this approach, protecting data from loss and theft is a joint obligation of cloud users and CSPs. Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are a popular strong encryption mechanism [6]. There are three stages for safeguarding private information for the customer:

- I. Data encryption in storage (encrypting the data on desk storage that protects data from illegally used and malicious CSP).
- II. Transient data encryption (encrypting confidential information such as credit cards while transmitting over the internet).
- III. Data encryption on backup media (whether internal or external storage) guards against unauthorized use of lost or stolen media.

5.2. Access Control Procedures (ACMs)

By rejecting, limiting, or restricting access to a system or an entity like processes, VMs, and VMMs in accordance with clearly established security standards, ACMs are in charge of safeguarding a VCCI. Mandatory Access Control (MAC), Discretionary Access Control (DAC), and Role-Based Access Control are the three ACMs most frequently employed in VCCI (RBAC). Since user subjects and resource objects may be uniquely identified by their names, all of these techniques are referred to as identity-based ACMs. Identification may take place directly or through the subjects' roles [7]. The resources' confidentiality and integrity are ensured by the ACMs.

5.3. VTP Module: Virtual Trusted Platform (vTPM)

It is based on a certificate chain that connects virtual TPMs to physical TPMs in order to give its capabilities and make it accessible to all VMs running on a platform. It was proposed by IBM researchers. In a certain layer above the hypervisor, vTPMs can be found. The vTPM Manager, which is integrated into each individual VM and has the ability to launch its own vTPM through the hypervisor, creates a vTPM instance for each one [8]. In order to extend the chain of trust from the hardware TPM to each vTPM, each VM has a corresponding vTPM instance that emulates the TPM functionality. This is done by carefully managing signing keys and certificates. In addition to certain software on the host, a vTPM has its own virtual Storage Root

Key (SRK) and Endorsement Key (EK). A physical TPM is virtualized via the system of vTPM in multi-tenant VCCI so that several VMs can use it on a single hardware platform.

5.4. Virtual Firewall (VF)

It is a firewall service that operates in a virtualized environment and offers the same packet filtering and monitoring functions as a physical firewall [9]. VFs can operate in bridge mode and hypervisor mode (hypervisor resident). Hypervisor-resident VFs must be implemented on the VMM, where they are responsible for catching harmful VM behaviors such as packet injections, in order to safeguard the VMs and VMM. These VFs call for a change to the hypervisor kernel of the physical host in order to install process hooks or modules that give the VF system access to VM data, direct access to the virtual networks, and virtualized network interfaces that transfer packet traffic between VMs. The same hooks may then be used by the hypervisor-resident VF to carry out all firewall operations, such as packet inspection, dropping, and forwarding, without ever having to interact with the virtual network. Because they execute packet inspection from within the kernel at native hardware rates rather than in VFs, hypervisor resident VFs can be quicker than bridge-mode VFs.

5.5. Reputable virtual domains (TVDs)

It is a security method developed at VCCI that groups linked virtual machines running on several physical machines into a single network domain with a single security policy. A shared resource policy allows for the coexistence of various TVD instances on a single platform. Since communication between TVDs only occurs in accordance with the security policies set by the administrator and specified in the VMM, the use of TVDs offers high isolation across unrelated VMs. A rogue VM cannot join any TVD since it must meet the policy's conditions in order to do so [10]. This prevents malicious VMs from harming trusted users' VMs in the cloud. The VMs that reside in a TVD are often identified by a special label. As an illustration, the VMs of one customer will have a different label from those of the other client. Labeling is used to identify the virtual machines (VMs) that have been allocated to a certain client and to let the same labeled VMs to run on the same TVD, which must be constructed in accordance with appropriate security principles and regulations that don't display any loopholes [11].

6.0. Conclusion and Recommendations For further research

Cloud computing faces a number of security difficulties, and it will be challenging to establish end-to-end security. We can see from the study above that VMM is a key target of the attack on VCCI for each client allocated with one or more virtual machines. However, it is much more complicated to deliver software for a million users to use as a service via a data center than it is to distribute software for a million users to run on their individual personal computers. Security must be applied at various layers of resources such as storage, network, and applications by taking resource management issues like SLAs (Service Level Agreements) into consideration. Depending on the effectiveness of the available resources and the cost of the cloud computing providers, our future study will examine different models and strategies for protecting VMM and VCCI.

References

- [1] Kulkarni, G., Chavan, N., Chandorkar, R., Waghmare, R., & Palwe, R. (2012). Cloud security challenges. *2012 7th International Conference on Telecommunication Systems, Services, and Applications (TSSA)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tssa.2012.6366028>
- [2] Zhang, L.-J., & Zhou, Q. (2009). CCOA: Cloud Computing Open Architecture. *2009 IEEE International Conference on Web Services*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icws.2009.144>
- [3] Dikaiakos, M. D., Katsaros, D., Mehra, P., Pallis, G., & Vakali, A. (2009). Cloud computing: Distributed internet computing for IT and scientific research. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 13(5), 10–13. <https://doi.org/10.1109/mic.2009.103>
- [4] Luo, S., Lin, Z., Chen, X., Yang, Z., & Chen, J. (2011). Virtualization security for cloud computing service. *2011 International Conference on Cloud and Service Computing*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/csc.2011.6138516>
- [5] Fu Wen, & Li Xiang. (2011). The study on Data Security in cloud computing based on virtualization. *2011 IEEE International Symposium on IT in Medicine and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/itime.2011.6132034>
- [6] Buyya, R., Garg, S. K., & Calheiros, R. N. (2011). SLA-oriented resource provisioning for cloud computing: Challenges, architecture, and solutions. *2011 International Conference on Cloud and Service Computing*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/csc.2011.6138522>
- [7] Cheng, L., Zhang, Y., & Han, Z. (2013). Quantitatively measure access control mechanisms across different operating systems. *2013 IEEE 7th International Conference on Software Security and Reliability*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/sere.2013.12>
- [9] Althobaiti, A. F. (2017). Analyzing security threats to Virtual Machines Monitor in cloud computing environment. *Journal of Information Security*, 08(01), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jis.2017.81001>
- [10] 2005 First Workshop on Secure Network Protocols (NPSEC). (2005). *1st IEEE ICNP Workshop on Secure Network Protocols, 2005. (NPSec)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/npsec.2005.1532040>
- [11] Iqbal, A., Pattinson, C., & Kor, A.-L. (2015). Performance Monitoring of Virtual Machines (VMS) of type I and II hypervisors with snmpv3. *2015 World Congress on Sustainable Technologies (WCST)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/wcst.2015.7415127>

